

ACADEMIC FREEDOM AND THE ISSUE OF FREEDOM OF SPEECH AND EXPRESSION IN MALAYSIA

Muzaffar Syah Mallow

Assoc. Prof. Dr., Faculty of Syariah & Law, Universiti Sains Islam Malaysia (USIM),
Bandar Baru Nilai, Negeri Sembilan Darul Khusus, Malaysia, Email:
muzaffarsyah.mallow@yahoo.com

Abstract

Whatever people perceptions, views and opinions have towards the issue of academic freedom, this is a very important issue which deserve serious attention by everyone. The issue of academic freedom has become a hot topic of discussion in many countries including Malaysia. This issue also has been highlighted in many developed countries including in the United States of America. In early 2025, the US President, Donald J. Trump has targeted few universities in the US just because these few universities did not share the same ideology, thought or thinking with him. The issue of academic freedom also received attention in Malaysia for the last many years. It is very important for us to understand the important of academic freedom. Why academic freedom is so important? Academic freedom is very important to ensure the country able to produce students with high qualities in order to bring constructive changes to the society and to the nation. Academic freedom is also important for the academicians. All countries need high quality academicians which can provide ideas for the nation building and development. It is very difficult for both students and academicians to contribute anything to the society or to the country without having academic freedom. In general, academic freedom means that both students and academicians can engage in intellectual debate or discussion without fear of censorship or retaliation. Academic freedom establishes a faculty member's right to remain true to his or her pedagogical philosophy and intellectual commitments. It preserves the intellectual integrity of our educational system and thus serves the public good. Academic freedom gives both students and academicians the right to express their views in speech, writing, and through electronic communication, both on and off campus without fear of sanction and prosecution from the authorities, unless the manner of expression substantially impairs the rights of others or the views demonstrate that they are professionally ignorant, incompetent, or dishonest with regard to their discipline or fields of expertise. Academic freedom also gives both students and academicians the right to study and do research on the topics they choose and to draw what conclusions they find consistent with their research, though it does not prevent others from judging whether their work is valuable and their conclusions sound. Thus, it is very crucial for us to cherish, respect and protect academic freedom at all times. Academic freedom should not be seen as a threat or enemy by anyone. When we discuss the issue over academic freedom, we cannot ignore the basic human right over freedom of speech and expression. These two types of freedoms are interrelated to each other. Thus, it is the object of this paper to examine and analyse these two types of freedoms. Recommendations will also be provided so that academic freedom could be guaranteed and protected.

Keywords: Academic, freedom, speech, expression, suppression

1. INTRODUCTION

Academic freedom is very important in order to ensure all types freedoms guaranteed under the human rights principles be respected and defended by everyone including by the respective educational institution, enforcement agencies and the government. Academic freedom is very crucial for all countries as it could assist the country to a better progress and development. Academic freedom also very vital to the society as it could bring many benefits for the society growth. It is very important for academic freedom to be cherish and treasured. We must not allow academic freedom be subjected to suppression. When we discussed about academic freedom, we should give our focus on what had happened in the United States of America under the second presidency of Donald J. Trump. Under the second presidency of Donald J. Trump, the federal government of the United States of America has sought to influence many aspects of education in the country. The Trump administration has sought to crack down on universities that it accuses of antisemitism and that it perceives as having a left-wing bias that discriminates against conservative students. The administration paused over US\$400 million in federal funding for Columbia University in March 2025 (Elena Moore, 2025), causing Columbia's leaders to agree to the government's demands, including the suspension or expulsion of students who participated in Columbia's 2024 pro-Palestinian campus occupations, taking steps to combat antisemitism at the university, and enacting changes to its admissions policies (Jake Offenhartz, 2025). The Trump administration also paused funding to many other universities; in April 2025, Harvard University publicly refused and criticized similar demands made by the Trump administration, filing a lawsuit against them and saying that the demands were an illegal overreach of government authority. In response, the administration paused over \$2 billion in funding for Harvard (Ariana Baio, 2025). However, on September 3, 2025, American Judge Allison D. Burroughs found that the funding freeze illegal, writing that the government had infringed upon Harvard's free speech rights and that it was "difficult to conclude anything other than that defendants used antisemitism as a smokescreen for a targeted, ideologically-motivated assault on this country's premier universities" (Michael T. Nietzel, 2025). In February 2025, Leo Terrell, the head of the Trump administration's Task Force to Combat Antisemitism, announced that he would investigate Columbia University, Harvard University, George Washington University, Johns Hopkins University, New York University, Northwestern University, University of California, Berkeley, UCLA, the University of Minnesota, and the University of Southern California as part of the Department of Justice's investigation into antisemitism on college campuses (Giselle Ruhyyah Ewing, 2025). Trump and many Republican officials in the country have even advocated for new laws and policies that crack down on campus curriculum and protests that they believe perpetuate a left-wing bias in universities and discriminate against conservative viewpoints (Jeremy W. Peters, 2025). The issue of academic freedom also received similar attention in Malaysia for the last many years. Recently, the state of Sabah drew national attention when several Universiti Malaysia Sabah (UMS) students at the "Gempur Rasuah Sabah 2.0" rally burned a caricature of the country Prime Minister, Anwar Ibrahim. Their purpose was clear namely to protest the 'Madani' government's failure to address corruption in Sabah, an issue that has long plagued the state. While their actions may seem radical, the spirit behind them is rooted in freedom of speech and expression and the idea over academic freedom. The students claim that their act was a criticism of hypocrisy, talks of integrity, yet no firm action against corruption in Sabah. Later, the police have confirmed the arrest of three individuals involved in the Gempur Rasuah Sabah 2.0 rally following the recording of their statements. Kota Kinabalu District Police Chief, Assistant Commissioner Kasim Muda, said the arrests were made at the Kota Kinabalu District Police Headquarters under the Sedition Act 1948 [Act 15] and in connection with the burning of a caricature of the Prime Minister during the rally. "After giving statements regarding the incident where a student's car was doused with acid during the Gempur Rasuah Sabah 2.0 rally, the three were arrested under the Sedition Act and for the burning of a caricature of the Prime Minister," he said when contacted by the local media. Earlier, two Universiti Malaysia Sabah (UMS) students and a former Universiti Malaysia Sabah (UMS) graduate had been called in to provide statements in connection with the acid attack on a student's vehicle, which reportedly occurred on the second day of the rally on June 22. It is understood that after their initial statements were taken, police proceeded to question the trio regarding their involvement in the rally, leading to their arrests (Borneo Post, 2025). Many seen the legal action against those students as an act against freedom of speech and expression as well as an obstruction to academic freedom (Mohd Azlim Zainury, 2025). Interestingly, the Prime Minister later seem to backed those students who are involved in the rally. Few days after the arrest event, the Prime ordered the country Higher Education Ministry (MOHE) and Universiti Malaysia Sabah (UMS) to ensure students involved in the recent Gempur Rasuah 2.0 rally in Kota Kinabalu may continue their studies freely. Announcing this, the senior press secretary to the Prime Minister, said that the Prime Minister understands that allowing dissent is an integral part of upholding democracy, given the latter's background as a student activist. "The burning of effigies of the prime minister

in Kota Kinabalu recently reminds us of the people's hope in us to eradicate corruption," the senior secretary said during a live-streamed briefing via Facebook. "(However), we cannot sacrifice the future of our youth simply because we have differences in opinion" (Dhesegaan Bala Krishnan, 2025).

Before the rally, there was also a complaint made by a student group which has accused the local Universiti Malaya (UM) of curtailing academic freedom by cancelling a forum scheduled for on whether Malaysia is a secular country or a religious country. The Universiti Malaya Association of New Youth (Umany) said it was instructed by the university's management yesterday to cancel the forum, purportedly on grounds that the discussion would touch on sensitive topics involving the 3Rs (Race, Religion and Royalty). The forum, entitled "Malaysia's Identity Crisis: Is Malaysia A Secular Country or a Religious Country?", was to be held at UM's Perdanasiswa Complex featuring constitutional lawyer Malik Imtiaz Sarwar and lawyer-activist Siti Kasim (Malaysiakini, 2025).

In 2024, there was a purportedly leaked memo from the local Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM) prohibiting academics from making public statements (Shahrin Aizat Noorshahrizam, 2024). A copy of the UKM circular dated Oct 8 and issued by Zainudin Daud, who is performing the duties of the university's registrar, is making the rounds on social media. The circular mandates that civil servants, including statutory body officers, refrain from making statements that could undermine government policies or embarrass government entities. Staff members were warned that violations could lead to disciplinary action (Free Malaysia Today, 2024). In the same year, the government produces a strong reminder to the public servants not to make any public statements without authorization. All civil servants are reminded not to make any public statements, including on social media, unless given the authority or mandate by their ministries or departments. In a post on the Public Services Department's (JPA) Facebook page, Chief Secretary to the Government Tan Sri Shamsul Azri Abu Bakar stated that the reminder was issued under the 2024 Prime Minister's Department's administrative meeting. "If found guilty and in violation of any regulation in effect, disciplinary action can be taken against the civil servant", he said in the post, which included information explaining that civil servants cannot make public statements that harm the government's policies, plans, or decisions on any issue, nor embarrass or discredit the government, either verbally or in writing. The ban is clearly outlined under Regulation 19(1) and 19(2) of the Public Officers (Conduct and Discipline) Regulations 1993 (New Straits Times, 2024). There are 1.7 million peoples working in the public services in the country which also includes academic working in the public universities.

Few years earlier, the country also been exposed with incident involving with one primary school teacher who have the courage and bravery to speak up against the government over the problems faced by school students. Fadli Salleh, better known as Cikgu Fadli had made the headlines in 2022 after revealing that he had received a letter from the education ministry's disciplinary board stating that he risked dismissal or demotion after repeatedly raising concerns over the primary school mathematics syllabus which he said was too advanced for the pupils. He had also highlighted the issue of children having to carry heavy school bags and said this was harmful to them. In October 2022, Cikgu Fadli told the local media that there was no point in continuing with his career unless there were wholesale changes in the education ministry (Free Malaysia Today, 2022).

In 2012, there was a sedition charged brought against University of Malaya law lecturer Azmi Sharom. Azmi was charged with sedition for remarks pertaining to the 2009 Perak constitutional crisis published in an online news portal on Aug 14, which he claimed was made based on academic discourse (Cynthia Ng, 2014). On September 2, 2014, Azmi claimed trial at a Sessions Court to the charge of making seditious comments on an online portal concerning the 2009 Perak crisis. An online portal had on Aug 14, 2014 published the comments of Azmi in an article titled Take Perak crisis route for speedy end to Selangor impasse. Azmi, who is also a columnist with The Star, was charged under Section 4(1)(b) of the Sedition Act, with an alternative charge under Section 4(1)(c) of the same Act. Section 4(1)(b) covers "uttering any seditious words" while Section 4(1)(c) deals with individuals who publish seditious publications, among other things. The Sessions Court however has acquitted and discharged him of the sedition charge. Deputy Public Prosecutor Ezrene Zakariah initially requested the court for Azmi to be given a discharge not amounting to an acquittal (DNAA). Defence counsel Gobind Singh Deo, however, argued that the case had been going on for 17 months and all prosecution witnesses had given their statements. "There is no reason for this case to continue as the Attorney-General has made a statement to withdraw the charge. It is unfair for this charge to be hanging over Azmi's head", said Gobind, adding that the A-G's decision to drop the charge was the correct one (Firdaous Fadzil, 2016). These are only few reported cases in the local media which highlights the concern over academic freedom in the country.

2. ACADEMIC FREEDOM AND THE ISSUE OF FREEDOM OF SPEECH AND EXPRESSION

Before going further, it is important for us to examine the concept of academic freedom. What is academic freedom? Academic freedom refers to the concept or principles that educators, researchers, and students should be free to teach, learn, and conduct research without fear of censorship, retaliation, or outside interference. It allows individuals in academic settings to pursue truth and knowledge, express ideas, and explore controversial topics without restrictions imposed by external authorities, such as governments, institutions, enforcement agencies or other groups. Academic freedom is fundamental to the integrity of education and research, enabling an open exchange of ideas and the pursuit of intellectual growth (Cobrief, 2024). Why academic freedom is important? Academic freedom is important because it fosters creativity, critical thinking, and the pursuit of knowledge. It allows academic institutions to remain independent, ensuring that research and teaching are based on facts, evidence, and open inquiry rather than political, social, or commercial pressures. Academic freedom also supports the diversity of thought, which is essential for innovation and the development of new ideas. Without academic freedom, the educational system could become stifled, and the ability to challenge prevailing ideas or explore new possibilities would be limited (Cobrief, 2024). Does academic freedom have anything to do with freedom of speech and expression? Yes, academic freedom is highly connected with freedom of speech and expression. Individual should be given the right to speak and express themselves without being subjected to unnecessary interrogation, arrest, prosecution and sentencing and this include those belong in the academic lines. Educators and students right to speak and express themselves should never be denied and suppress. Freedom of speech and expression is part of basic human right. The right to freedom of speech and expression has been recognized as a human right in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) and international human rights law. Many countries including Malaysia have constitutional laws that protect freedom of speech and expression for their people. Terms such as free speech, freedom of speech, and freedom of expression are often used interchangeably in political discourse. However, in legal contexts, freedom of expression more broadly encompasses the right to seek, receive, and impart information or ideas, regardless of the medium used. Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) states that “everyone shall have the right to hold opinions without interference and everyone shall have the right to freedom of expression; this right shall include freedom to seek, receive, and impart information and ideas of all kinds, regardless of frontiers” (United Nations, 2025). This either orally, in writing or print, in the form of art, or through any other media of his or her choice. In Malaysia, freedom of speech and expression has also been guaranteed under the country highest law namely the Federal Constitution. Article 10 of the Malaysia Federal Constitution guarantees Malaysian citizens the right to freedom of speech, freedom of assembly and freedom of association. Since academic freedom and freedom of speech and expression been seen by many as interconnected to each other, we should regard academic freedom as part of the basic human right.

However, we must also take note that no freedom can be absolute including freedom of speech and expression. The version of Article 19 in the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) later amends Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) by stating that the exercise of these rights carries “special duties and responsibilities and may therefore be subject to certain restrictions” when necessary [f]or respect of the rights or reputation of others or [f]or the protection of national security or public order (ordre public), or of public health or morals” (United Nations, 2025). Similarly, under the Malaysia Federal Constitution limitation also been imposed over freedom of speech and expression. Article 10 (2) (a) states that on the rights conferred by paragraph (a) of Clause (1) over freedom of speech and expression, “Parliament may by law impose restrictions as it deems necessary or expedient in the interest of the security of the Federation or any part thereof, friendly relations with other countries, public order or morality and restrictions designed to protect the privileges of Parliament or of any Legislative Assembly or to provide against contempt of court, defamation, or incitement to any offence”. Common limitations or boundaries to freedom of speech and expression relate to libel, slander, obscenity, pornography, sedition, incitement, fighting words, hate speech, classified information, copyright violation, trade secrets, food labeling, non-disclosure agreements, the right to privacy, dignity, the right to be forgotten, public security, blasphemy and perjury. Justifications for such include the harm principle, proposed by John Stuart Mill in *On Liberty*, which suggests that “the only purpose for which power can be rightfully exercised over any member of a civilized community, against his will, is to prevent harm to others” (David Van Mill, 2016). Although academic freedom and freedom of speech and expression is given to us, it should be use with full responsibility. People must never use such freedoms to create chaos and bring harms to anyone. Having said so, though such freedoms is not absolute, it does not mean the authority can simply do whatever they

want to suppress such freedoms. Authority should not constantly enforce existing laws to make an arrest and prosecute anyone for speaking and expressing themselves. Authority should not create so many laws and regulations to hamper such freedoms. There is also a fear that many laws and regulations been created not to ensure freedom of speech and expression been used responsibly but rather to protect the authority themselves so that they can remain in power for eternity.

3. THE LAW AND PRACTICE IN MALAYSIA OVER ACADEMIC FREEDOM AND THE ISSUE ON FREEDOM OF SPEECH AND EXPRESSION

There are varieties of legislations which we can refer to when we talk about academic freedom and the issue over freedom of speech and expression in Malaysia. However, two main pieces of legislations play very important role on such matter namely the Universities and University Colleges Act 1971 [Act 30] and the Sedition Act 1948 [Act 15]. The Universities and University Colleges Act 1971 [Act 30], widely known by local as AUKU 1971, also as UUCA or as Act No. 30, is a general legislation for the establishment of government supported universities in the country. It was passed by the Malaysian parliament in 1971 and went into effect on 30 April the same year. The government body that is responsible for the implementation of this Act is the Ministry of Higher Education (MOHE). It is a template legislation that sets out the procedures for the establishment of government universities, the legal status of the universities, their governance structure and the regulation of staff and students. According to the Malaysian Academic Movement (GERAK), at one time, universities could only be established under the UUCA, which established a government monopoly over the formation of universities. Today, because of changes in higher education policies over the last 50 years, universities can be established with the same ease as registering a company. The Private Higher Educational Institutions Act 1996 [Act 555] provides a simple mechanism for anyone to establish a private university. Policy decisions have also seen universities and higher education institutions being established by Acts of Parliament such as UITM (under the Universiti Teknologi MARA Act 1976 [Act 173]). Teacher education colleges, polytechnics and vocational colleges are established under the Education Act 1996 [Act 550], the same Act also establishes the National Education System (GERAK, 2022). The Universities and University Colleges Act 1971 [Act 30] is a piece of legislation which had faced with many controversial issues over the matter involving academic freedom and the issue over freedom of speech and expression. In 2023, a public university student alliance wants a rethink on the Universities and University Act 1971 [Act 30] which it says continues to curtail freedom of speech and expression. The New Students Movement Alliance of Malaysia (Nesa) wants more autonomy for the higher institutions of learning. The AUKU has been amended seven times since it was gazetted in 1971. The last amendment was in 2019. The Malaysian government has made a statement that it had no plans to abolish AUKU. But it added it was looking to improve the act so that university students will have more freedom to participate in political activities. "The ministry is of the view that the existing act is still relevant in enforcing its functions, especially for matters related to university governance. "The repeal of AUKU will affect the governance of public universities, especially during the transition of the act. "In fact, this repeal process requires further research since it involves several other Acts that are also in force, for example the Private Higher Education Institutions Act 1996 [Act 555], the Education Act 1996 [Act 550], the Statutory Bodies (Discipline and Surcharge) Act 2000 [Act 605] and several other acts supervised under other ministries or agencies "However, the ministry is always open to any suggestion to improve the act," it said (Angie Tan, 2023). In 2025, Pakatan Harapan (PH) Youth stated that they will establish a special committee to continue efforts to push for the Universities and University Colleges Act 1971 [Act 30] to be abolished. The wing's information chief Ammar Atan said the committee would be drafting a plan for AUKU to be abolished as part of its reform agenda for the higher education system. While the Act was originally formulated to provide a centralised framework for the expansion of higher education in the country, its restrictions on university autonomy and students' freedom of expression have made it the subject of contentious debate. "PH Youth believes that abolishing AUKU is an important step in elevating the dignity of students and providing them with greater academic and political freedom," said Ammar in a statement. Abolishing the Act was part of PH's manifesto in the 14th and 15th general elections. Last March, higher education minister Zambry Abd Kadir told the Dewan Rakyat that improving sections of Auku was more realistic than abolishing the Act. He explained that abolishing Auku would result in the creation of new constitutions in each public university, which would take time and disrupt operations (Muhammad Yusri Muzamir, 2025 and Venesa Devi, 2025). There have many demands from local students for the AUKU act to be repeal and abolish entirely in order to strengthen academic freedom and freedom of speech and expression in the country. However, the Malaysian government still maintain with their view that such Act is still needed and the best they can do is to make amendment to the Act instead of repeal or abolish it entirely. This creates a dilemma between local education institution and the government until today.

Beside that, we need to focus to the Sedition Act 1948 [Act 15]. This particular piece of legislation is much old than the above-mentioned statute. It has been around in the country before the country gained its independence from the British colonial in 1957. Sedition Act 1948 [Act 15] was created in order to deal with the severe political and social disturbance which the country had after the Second World War and before the independence namely the communist insurgence (Jennifer Park, 2014). At the same time, The British also need such Act to protect their own colonial interest in the country back than which was known as British Malaya. This law prohibiting discourse deemed as seditious. This law has been enforced in the country until today. Sedition Act 1948 [Act 15] can be use against anyone in the country including against academician and students. The existence of such act can be seen hampering academic freedom in the country. People unable to express their minds, views and opinions daringly because the existence of such Act. They afraid of being interrogated, arrested, prosecuted and punish under such Act. According to Section 4 of the Sedition Act 1948 [Act 15] any person who (a) does or attempts to do, or makes any preparation to do, or conspires with any person to do, any act which has or which would, if done, have a seditious tendency; (b) utters any seditious words; (c) prints, publishes, sells, offers for sale, distributes or reproduces any seditious publication; or (d) imports any seditious publication, shall be guilty of an offence and shall, on conviction, be liable for a first offence to a fine not exceeding five thousand ringgit or to imprisonment for a term not exceeding three years or to both, and, for a subsequent offence, to imprisonment for a term not exceeding five years; and any seditious publication found in the possession of the person or used in evidence at his trial shall be forfeited and may be destroyed or otherwise disposed of as the court directs. (2) Any person who without lawful excuse has in his possession any seditious publication shall be guilty of an offence and shall, on conviction, be liable for a first offence to a fine not exceeding two thousand ringgit or to imprisonment for a term not exceeding eighteen months or to both, and, for a subsequent offence, to imprisonment for a term not exceeding three years, and the publication shall be forfeited and may be destroyed or otherwise disposed of as the court directs. Sedition Act 1948 [Act 15] has been heavily criticised by the Amnesty International in their yearly report. According to Amnesty International reports released in 2024, Malaysia continues to use restrictive laws to curtail freedom of expression and assembly. The report highlights the shrinking space for freedom of expression in Malaysia, with increased censorship, harassment, and restrictions on peaceful assembly. The use of repressive laws continued to stifle dissent and curtail freedom of speech in 2023. According to Amnesty International, "What has been deeply disappointing is that the government has failed to fulfil its commitments to reform laws that restrict the right to freedom of expression as it had committed to do in its pre-election manifesto. Completely backtracking on its commitment, the government has instead continued to use these laws to silence critical voices and prevent peaceful protest". A government that says it is "reform-minded" needs to be honest about how laws have been used to stifle expression and political participation and should have the integrity to fulfil its commitments to repealing draconian laws such as the Sedition Act 1948 [Act 15] (Ameera Huda, 2024).

4. RECOMMENDATION

If we want to bring the society and country forward to a better future, it is important for us to cherish and protect academic freedom and freedom of speech and expression. There is no other way. There are some laws in the country which need to be visited, analyses, repeal entirely in order to ensure the existence of such freedoms. Worth to note, there is no single legislation or provision which protect academic freedom in the country. The time has come for the country to see this issue seriously and take concrete step to protect such freedom. There was an undergoing effort carried out by the Ministry of Higher Education (MOHE) to create a guideline over academic freedom (Qistina Sallehuddin and Fuad Nizam, 2025). However, there is a fear that such guidelines might be subjected to abuse later by the management and authority to curtail academic freedom and freedom of speech and expression. Question need to be asked, why we need to create a guideline for what and what not to say? Why do we still need to control people speech and expression? What will happen if a person said something which does not please the ruling government? The present of a guideline can be seen as an addition to the existing laws which suppress academic freedom and freedom of speech and expression. There is a concern that people will no longer have the courage or bravery to speak out anymore. Instead of creating guidelines and laws controlling or supervising such matter, we should create a clear policy and regulations which can guarantee academic freedom and freedom of speech and expression. All educational institution in the country including schools, colleges and universities should have a clear policy which guarantee academic freedom as well as freedom of speech and expression. The time has come for us to have a difference mindset over the matter. Any difference views or opinions should be discussed professionally through meetings, talks or debates and not through legal repercussion like arrest, prosecution and imprisonment.

REFERENCE LIST

- Academic freedom: Overview, definition, and example. (2024). <https://www.cobrief.app/resources/legal-glossary/academic-freedom-overview-definition-and-example/>. Cobrief. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.
- Ameera Huda. (2024). 'Unsalvageable' Sedition Act must be abolished, say rights groups. <https://www.freemalaysiatoday.com/category/nation/2024/04/03/unsalvageable-sedition-act-must-be-abolished-say-rights-groups>. Free Malaysia Today. Retrieved on 1 October 2025.
- Angie Tan. (2023). Student group tells govt to abolish oppressive university act. <https://www.themalaysianinsight.com/s/430120>. Malaysian Insight. Retrieved on 1 October 2025.
- Ariana Baio. (2025). Trump administration slashes \$2.2bn in federal money from Harvard after it refuses president's 'dictates'. <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/world/americas/us-politics/harvard-university-reject-trump-funds-b2733234.html>. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.
- Cynthia Ng. (2014). Sedition charge against Prof Azmi restricts academic freedom – Saifuddin. <https://international.astroawani.com/malaysia-news/sedition-charge-against-prof-azmi-restricts-academic-freedom-saifuddin-43261>. Astro Awani. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.
- Civil servants reminded not to make public statements, including on socmed – JPA. (2024). <https://www.nst.com.my/news/nation/2024/10/1115013/civil-servants-reminded-not-make-public-statements-including-socmed-jpa>. New Straits Times. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.
- David Van Mill. (2016). Freedom of Speech. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2016/entries/freedom-speech/>. The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. Retrieved on 30 September 2025. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.
- Dhesegaan Bala Krishnan. (2025). Anwar backs students' right to protest, tells MoHE and UMS to protect academic freedom. <https://www.malaymail.com/news/malaysia/2025/06/24/anwar-backs-students-right-to-protest-tells-mohe-and-ums-to-protect-academic-freedom/181545>. Malay Mail. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.
- Elena Moore. (2025). Trump administration cancels \$400 million in federal dollars for Columbia University. <https://www.npr.org/2025/03/07/nx-s1-5321326/trump-administration-columbia-university-400-million-cancelled>. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.
- Firdaus Fadzil. (2016). Court acquits Azmi Sharom of sedition charge. <https://www.malaysianbar.org.my/article/news/legal-and-general-news/legal-news/court-acquits-azmi-sharom-of-sedition-charge>. Malaysian Bar. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.
- Gerak admin. (2022). About AUKU* Universities and University Colleges Act 1971 (Act 30). <https://gerak-akademik.org/academic-freedom-legal-frameworks/about-aukuuniversities-and-university-colleges-act-1971-act-30>. GERAK. Retrieved on 1 October 2025.
- Giselle Ruhyyah Ewing. (2025). Meet the former Democrat leading Trump's charge against 10 universities. <https://www.politico.com/news/2025/05/23/leo-terrell-trump-universities-harvard-00368352>. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.
- International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. (2025). <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/international-covenant-civil-and-political-rights>. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.
- Jake Offenhartz. (2025). Under threat from Trump, Columbia University agrees to policy changes. <https://apnews.com/article/columbia-university-funding-trump-fa70143c715df8fd4ef337c0e1ccf872>. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.
- Jennifer Park. (2014). What is Malaysia's sedition law? <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-29373164>. BBC News. Retrieved on 1 October 2025.
- Jeremy W. Peters. (2025). How the G.O.P. went from championing campus free speech to fighting it. <https://www.nytimes.com/2025/03/20/us/politics/republicans-trump-free-speech-campus.html>. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.
- Mohd Azlim Zainury. (2025). Tindakan terhadap pelajar UMS perlu dikaji semula – Lawyers for Liberty.

<https://www.sinarharian.com.my/article/735324/berita/semasa/tindakan-terhadap-pelajar-ums-perlu-dikaji-semula-ndash-lawyers-for-liberty>. Sinar Harian. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.

Michael T. Nietzel. (2025). In win for higher Ed, Judge rules Harvard funding freeze is illegal. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/michaelt Nietzel/2025/09/04/in-win-for-higher-ed-judge-rules-harvard-funding-freeze-is-illegal/>. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.

Muhammad Yusri Muzamir. (2025). Angkatan Muda Harapan saran AUKU dimansuh. <https://www.bharian.com.my/berita/nasional/2025/06/1412633/angkatan-muda-harapan-saran-auku-dimansuh>. Berita Harian. Retrieved on 1 October 2025.

MP slams UKM for banning statements on govt policies by staff. (2024). <https://www.freemalaysiatoday.com/category/nation/2024/10/17/mp-slams-ukm-for-banning-statements-on-govt-policies-by-staff>. Free Malaysia Today. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.

Qistina Sallehuddin and Fuad Nizam. (2025). Guidelines on academic freedom being finalized. <https://www.nst.com.my/news/nation/2025/08/1259774/guidelines-academic-freedom-being-finalised>. New Straits Times. Retrieved on 1 October 2025.

Shahrin Aizat Noorshahrizam. (2024). Ex-minister slams 'leaked UKM memo' silencing academics. <https://www.malaysiakini.com/news/723001>. Malaysiakini. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.

Student group accuses UM of shutting down forum. (2025). <https://www.malaysiakini.com/news/740806>. Malaysiakini. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.

Teacher threatened with dismissal for highlighting problematic syllabus retires. (2025). <https://www.freemalaysiatoday.com/category/nation/2024/02/07/teacher-threatened-with-dismissal-for-highlighting-problematic-syllabus-retires>. Free Malaysia Today. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.

Three arrested over Gempur Rasuah Sabah 2.0 rally, police confirm. (2025). <https://www.theborneopost.com/2025/06/24/three-arrested-over-gempur-rasuah-sabah-2-0-rally-police-confirm/>. Borneo Post. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.

Universal Declaration of Human Rights. (2025). <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>. United Nations. Retrieved on 30 September 2025.

Venesa Devi. (2025). File motion against PM if you must, but stop making excuses, PH Youth tells Opposition. <https://www.thestar.com.my/news/nation/2025/08/08/file-motion-against-pm-if-you-must-but-stop-making-excuses-ph-youth-tells-opposition>. The Star. Retrieved on 1 October 2025.